

New record of a rice leaf miner, *Pseudonapomyza asiatica* Spencer (Diptera: Agromyzidae), in the Philippines

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Observations on rice seedlings in Iloilo, Pangasinan, and Laguna provinces, Philippines, in 1977 and 1978 revealed the presence of an unknown leaf miner. The same leaf miner attacked transplanted and direct-seeded rice. The mines (10–42 mm long, and 1–4 mm wide) run parallel to the leaf blade and usually occur at the apices. Each dissected leaf mine had a single white larva 0.8 to 2.0 mm long. The larva pupated within the mine, protected by the upper and lower epidermis of the leaf. The puparium, 1.35 mm long and 0.65 mm wide, appears mat, and each segment boundary is marked by 4 or 5 rows of irregularly placed spines. The puparium is generally glued firmly within the mine. Adult flies that emerged from infested leaves bearing pupae were identified as *Pseudonapomyza asiatica* Spencer by Dr. M. Sasakawa of Kyoto Prefectural University, Japan. The adults can be distinguished from related species by the bluntly angulate third antennal segment, mat mesonotum, grayish orbits, black lateral sides of thorax, largely colorless M 1 + 2 and M 3 + 4, and the squamae and fringe are conspicuously silvery white. *P. asiatica* is widely distributed in Asia but this is the first account of its being a rice pest in the Philippines. Another host, *Cynodon dactylon*, was reported in Singapore in 1961. *Pseudonapomyza atra* has been mentioned as a leaf miner on rice in India and Taiwan, but according to taxonomists it is distributed in the temperate regions of North America and Europe. Therefore, the early records of *P. atra* in Asia probably referred to *P. asiatica*.

Photo 1 Rice leaves with damage (mines) and pupae of *P. asiatica*.

Photo 2 Adult fly